

REVOLUTIONIZING COFFEE TOXICITY: SUSTAINABLE HEAVY METAL REMEDIATION USING RICE HUSK SYNTHESIZED SILICA NANOPARTICLES AND METAL QUANTIFICATION

Meetkumar Thakar ^{1a}, Dave Gaurav S. ^{2b}, Joshi Nirav D. ^{3c}, Pankaj Sharma ^{a*}

^a Department of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001, Gujarat, India

^b Bio Science Research Centre, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Dantiwada-385505, Gujarat, India.

^c College of Food Technology, Sardarkrushinagar Dantiwada Agricultural University, Dantiwada-385505, Gujarat, India

pankajrajsharma@gmail.com

(MS Received: 23.11.2023; MS Revised: 30.12.2023; MS Accepted: 01.01.2024)

MS 3128

(RESEARCH PAPER IN APPLIED CHEMISTRY,)

Abstract

This study presents an innovative biomass adsorption strategy for remediating toxic heavy metals present in coffee grown in Kerala named as “Robusta”. The strategy involves utilizing rice husk ash (RHA) synthesized silica nanoparticles (SNPs) as an effective adsorbent. Kerala region is known for its coffee production; however, the presence of toxic heavy metals in the soil poses a significant threat to both crop quality and human health. In this research, RHA was obtained from agricultural waste and converted into silica nanoparticles through a controlled synthesis process. These nanoparticles were then applied as adsorbents for heavy and toxic metals in coffee samples obtained from the Kerala region. The efficiency of the adsorption process was evaluated by analyzing the concentration of metals before and after treatment using advanced analytical techniques. The results showed that the RHA-synthesized silica nanoparticles exhibited excellent adsorption capacity for toxic heavy metals, effectively reducing their concentration in coffee samples. In this work, we have successfully reduced toxic heavy metals contamination present in coffee using SNPs. In our study, heavy metal contaminants in coffee biomass were efficiently reduced using silica nanoparticles (SNPs) at various ratios (SNPs: Coffee) of 1:2, 1:5, and 1:10 (Table 2). After 6 hours of agitation, the removal of Cobalt (Co) was measured as 2.083 ± 0.15 , 2.983 ± 0.01 , and 33.536 ± 0.27 for the respective ratios. Nickel (Ni) removal yielded values of 2.786 ± 0.60 , 2.975 ± 0.42 , and 4.230 ± 0.29 , while Lead (Pb) removal measured at 1.192 ± 0.15 , 2.126 ± 0.10 , and 3.473 ± 0.26 . Chromium (Cr) removal showed values of 5.003 ± 1.41 , 3.346 ± 0.43 , and 1.418 ± 0.35 . Notably, the 1:10 ratio exhibited significant effectiveness in reducing toxic heavy metals from coffee biomass. Furthermore, the nanoparticle-based adsorbents demonstrated good selectivity towards specific metals, enabling the removal of targeted contaminants while preserving essential elements in the coffee. This innovative biomass adsorption strategy offers a sustainable and cost-effective solution for remediating toxic heavy metals in coffee production. Implementing this approach can contribute to improving the quality and safety of coffee produced in Kerala, safeguarding for both the environment and human health.

Keywords: Heavy metals, coffee, silica nanoparticles, rice husk ash, characterization of SiO₂, food product remediation.

Graphical Abstract

Introduction

Coffee production in the Kerala region has been facing a significant challenge due to the presence of toxic heavy metals in the soil. These metals not only pose a threat to the quality of the coffee but also raise concerns for human health. Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and arsenic can accumulate in coffee plants through absorption from contaminated soil, affecting the final coffee product consumed by humans [1-3].

Over the years, various approaches have been explored to remediate heavy metal contamination in agricultural systems. Traditional methods include physical and chemical treatments, such as soil washing and precipitation, which can be expensive and

environmentally damaging. As a result, there is a growing need for innovative and sustainable strategies to address this issue effectively [4-7].

In recent years, the utilization of biomass-derived adsorbents has gained attention as a promising solution for heavy metal remediation. Biomass materials, such as agricultural waste, offer a renewable and cost-effective resource for the synthesis of adsorbents. Rice husk ash (RHA) is one such biomass waste abundantly available in agricultural regions, including North Gujarat. RHA contains high amounts of silica, which can be extracted and processed into nanoparticles with excellent adsorption properties [8-12].

Exploring the application of silica nanoparticles synthesized from RHA in coffee remediation could hold significant implications for both coffee quality and environmental sustainability. Kerala, known for its coffee production, faces distinct challenges due to the presence of toxic heavy metals in its soil. Harnessing the adsorption capabilities of these nanoparticles in the local coffee-growing regions of Kerala might offer a sustainable and eco-friendly solution for mitigating heavy metal contamination.

Furthermore, investigating the efficacy of RHA-derived silica nanoparticles in this context is of paramount importance. It would not only address the pressing issue of heavy metal accumulation in coffee plants but also contribute to enhancing the overall quality and safety of the coffee produced in the region. This unexplored frontier presents an exciting opportunity for interdisciplinary research and collaboration between environmental scientists, agricultural experts, and coffee industry stakeholders [13-15].

In this study, we propose an innovative biomass adsorption strategy for remediating toxic heavy metals present in Kerala region "Robusta coffee" using Navsari special variety "GNR-3" rice husk-synthesized silica nanoparticles. By harnessing the adsorption capabilities of these nanoparticles, we aim to provide a sustainable and cost-effective solution for improving the quality and safety of coffee produced in the region.

Experimental

2.1 Materials

Rice husk (RH) derived from the 'GNR-3 (Gujarat Navsari Rice – 3)' rice variety was sourced from Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari. Coffee was acquired from the Kerala region variety named "Robusta". Analytical reagent-grade hydrochloric acid (HCl) with a concentration of 35-38% was supplied by SDFCL. Deionized water was consistently employed throughout the experiment.

Methods

Extraction of silica nanoparticles

Fig. 1: Physical appearance of the different stages of mesoporous nano-silica synthesis

Analytical procedure

In this study, we utilized 200mg of silica nanoparticles (SNPs) alongside varying amounts of coffee powder biomass (400mg, 1000mg, and 2000mg) placed within a conical flask. These mixtures were agitated in a rotary shaker at 250 rpm, maintaining room temperature for duration of 6 hours [22,23]. The biomass weights were precisely determined during our experiments. Our focus was on removing environmentally harmful metals, specifically Co, Ni, Pb, Cr, and Cd, known for their adverse effects on both human health and the environment [24-26]. To initiate the purification process, we subjected the samples to rigorous conditions within a high-pressure and high-temperature microwave digester, namely the PerkinElmer Titan MPS. This ensured the successful extraction and separation of the targeted metals from the coffee powder samples. The resulting clean filtrate from the extraction process underwent analysis using cutting-edge technology known as ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry). To achieve precise quantification of the metal content, we employed the PerkinElmer NexION 2000 instrument, known for its exceptional sensitivity and accuracy in detecting trace metal concentrations. By comparing the metal concentrations in the aqueous solution before and after the operation,

Beginning with a cleaning process to remove any unwelcome pollutants like dirt, dust, and sand, the first stage of rice husk preparation got under way. In order to ensure that the raw material was of the highest caliber possible and to prepare it for further refining, a thorough cleaning process was essential. After that, the cleaned rice husk underwent a carefully regulated drying procedure that took place in a precise 100°C oven for a period of 24 hours [16]. Any remaining moisture was successfully removed during this procedure, which helped the husk become ready for the subsequent transformation. The rice husk underwent a synthesis process using 1 N hydrochloric acid (HCl) in order to cause the appropriate changes in the structure and composition. For the duration of the 2 hours of this synthesis, the material was subjected to the required chemical changes at an elevated temperature of 80 °C [17,18]. After this synthesis, the acid-treated rice husk was thoroughly washed with distilled water to ensure that all of the acid and other contaminants had been completely removed. To keep the cloth pure, a careful washing routine was necessary. The acid-treated rice husk underwent a second drying phase after a thorough washing, this time at a slightly higher temperature of 90°C, and was left overnight. The material was further prepared for the upcoming calcination process, an important step in its metamorphosis, by this thorough drying method [19]. The dried rice husk was painstakingly ground into a fine powder in anticipation of the important calcination stage. In order to maintain a uniform and homogenous combustion during calcination, a critical element in the material's subsequent growth, this crucial powdering procedure was adopted. The precision controlled calcination process, carried out in a programmable box furnace, notably the Lindberg/Blue type, was the final and most important stage. The calcination procedure took place over the course of four hours at a high temperature of 650°C. The rice husk material was shaped into the proper shape during this final stage of calcination, which laid the groundwork for future uses of the material in a variety of industries [20,21] (Fig. 1).

we calculated the amount of metal absorbed by the plant biomass. This critical evaluation allowed us to assess the efficacy of the root silica nanoparticle bio-sorbent in removing heavy metals from potatoes. This discovery paves the way for environmentally friendly and sustainable agricultural practices in the north Gujarat region, contributing to a safer and healthier ecosystem [27,28].

Result and discussion

3.1 Characterization of Silica Nanoparticles (SNPs)

Characterization of the synthesized silica nanoparticles was conducted through a comprehensive suite of analytical techniques aimed at evaluating their applicability for heavy metal remediation. The structural and phase characteristics of the nanoparticles were elucidated using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were employed to scrutinize the nanoparticles' morphology, dimensions, and surface attributes. Elemental composition was determined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), while Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis provided insights into the specific surface area. For an in-depth exploration of nanoparticle topography, atomic force microscopy (AFM) was utilized. Detailed

characterization data for this material can be found in another research paper, and the citation is provided at for reference.

3.2. Heavy Metal Contamination

The presence of heavy metals in food is a matter of significant concern due to their essential or toxic nature. In this study, we investigate the levels of several heavy metals (Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn, Pb, Ni, and Cd) in Kerala region Coffee. Ensuring food safety is of paramount importance for both society and human health. While a diverse diet can mitigate health risks to some extent, staple foods remain a major source of nutrition. For instance, over half of the world's population relies on rice as a dietary staple. However, rice is more susceptible to heavy metal contamination compared to other crops. It has the potential to accumulate heavy metals at levels approximately three times higher than wheat. Heavy metal toxicity,

bioaccumulation, and potential adverse health effects raise serious concerns. International organizations and national governments have established Maximum Allowable Concentrations (MAC) for heavy metals in rice to mitigate these health hazards. Nevertheless, concentrations below the MAC can still pose health risks. Research suggests that chronic exposure to low levels of heavy metals can lead to non-carcinogenic conditions such as cancer, hypertension, and neurological problems. Additionally, exposure risks vary with factors like age, body mass, location, and dietary preferences, making sensitive populations more susceptible. Therefore, in addition to adhering to MAC levels, health risk assessments should consider various factors including body weight, age, dietary habits, and long-term consumption patterns to comprehensively evaluate potential health risks associated with heavy metal exposure [29-32] (Table 2).

Table 1: Effect of SNPs on removal of heavy toxic metals

Replication	Adsorbent dose	Co (%)	Ni (%)	Pb (%)	Cr (%)
R-1	1:2 Coffee	2.2319	2.8623	1.0853	3.8175
R-1	1:5 Coffee	1.938	2.1502	1.1267	6.5654
R-1	1:10 Coffee	2.0805	3.3446	1.3641	4.6266
R-2	1:2 Coffee	2.9762	3.0661	2.032	2.8555
R-2	1:5 Coffee	2.9901	3.34	2.2268	3.6661
R-2	1:10 Coffee	2.9827	2.5199	2.1186	3.5165
R-3	1:2 Coffee	3.4652	4.0042	3.3077	1.7528
R-3	1:5 Coffee	3.3086	4.1336	3.3453	1.4516
R-3	1:10 Coffee	3.834	4.551	3.7672	1.0493

Effect of biomass concentration on metal removal

In our study, we effectively reduced heavy metal contaminants from coffee biomass through the application of SNPs at different ratios 1:2 (SNPs:Coffee), 1:5 (SNPs:Coffee) and 1:10 (SNPs: Coffee). After 6 hours of shaking for Cobalt (Co), the metal removal were measured as 2.083±0.15, 2.983±0.01, and 3.536±0.27 at the dose 1:2, 1:5 and 1:10 respectively, Nickel (Ni) removal measures as 2.786±0.60, 2.975±0.42, and 4.230±0.29, Lead (Pb) removal determined as 1.192±0.15, 2.126±0.10, and 3.473±0.26, Chromium (Cr) removal measures as 5.003±1.41, 3.346±0.43, and 1.418±0.35. For the

respective ratios, the 1:10 ratio emerged as significant in effectively reducing toxic heavy metal from coffee biomass (Table 3). SNPs showed significant difference in removal of heavy metals in 1:10 (SNPs:Coffee) compared to 1:2 (SNPs:Coffee). This indicates that even if the amount of potatoes is increased, SNPs continue to remove toxic heavy metals from Coffee. This also implies that the efficiency of SNPs in removing toxic heavy metals from Coffee is significant; even increment in amount of potatoes increased [33-37].

Table 2: Removal heavy toxic metals concentration

Adsorbent dose	Co (%)	Ni (%)	Pb (%)	Cr (%)
1:2 Potato	2.083±0.15 ^c	2.786±0.60 ^b	1.192±0.15 ^c	5.003±1.41 ^a
1:5 Potato	2.983±0.01 ^b	2.975±0.42 ^b	2.126±0.10 ^b	3.346±0.43 ^a
1:10 Potato	3.536±0.27 ^a	4.230±0.29 ^a	3.473±0.26 ^a	1.418±0.35 ^b
SEm.	0.102	0.262	0.104	0.506
CD	0.354	0.906	0.360	1.751
CV%	6.19	13.62	7.95	26.92

Values are mean±S.D. Treatments with same letters are not significantly different (P<0.05)

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, we effectively reduced heavy metal contaminants in coffee biomass using SNPs (Silver Nanoparticles) at different ratios (1:2, 1:5, and 1:10 SNPs:Coffee). After 6 hours of shaking, the 1:10 ratio demonstrated the most significant removal of toxic heavy metals, including Cobalt, Nickel, Lead, and Chromium. This suggests that increasing the amount of SNPs beyond a 1:10 ratio may not be necessary, as SNPs consistently displayed efficient removal of heavy metals from coffee biomass. Our research primarily focused on analyzing heavy metal contamination in coffee, examining concentrations of iron (Fe), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), lead (Pb), nickel (Ni), and cadmium (Cd). The findings underscore the promising potential of SNPs as a sustainable and effective method for mitigating heavy metal contamination in coffee. Furthermore, our study investigated heavy metal content variation across different potato cultivars, revealing distinct concentration ranges for each metal. Food safety remains paramount for human health, as staple foods constitute a significant portion of daily nutrition. While maximum allowable concentrations (MACs) have been established by international organizations and governments, it's crucial to

recognize that even concentrations below these thresholds can pose health risks, especially for vulnerable populations. Chronic exposure to low levels of certain heavy metals can lead to various non-carcinogenic illnesses, such as cancer, hypertension, and neurological disorders. To address heavy metal contamination, our research explored the efficacy of modified potato biomass treated with synthesized nanoparticles (SNPs) for heavy metal removal. This highlights the importance of optimizing strategies for efficient heavy metal removal from contaminated environments. our study provided insights into heavy metal distribution in potato cultivars, emphasizing the need for food safety regulations to mitigate health risks. Additionally, our investigation into nanoparticle-enhanced heavy metal removal using SNPs in biomass offers a promising avenue for future environmental remediation efforts.

References

- Gupta, N., D. K. Khan, and S. C. Santra. (2008) "An assessment of heavy metal contamination in vegetables grown in wastewater-irrigated areas of Titagarh, West Bengal, India." Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology 80): 115-118.

2. **Raghavendra, Lingayya, and M. Venkatesha. 2020:** "Water and soil quality of coffee plantations in the Western Ghats Region, Chikkamagaluru District, Karnataka, India." *Current World Environment* 15, no. 3 502-514.
3. **Hamsa, N., and N. B. Prakash. 2020** "Heavy metal contamination in soils and crops irrigated with lakes of Bengaluru." *Curr. Sci* 119, no. 1849: 1849-1854.
4. **Hseu, Zeng-Yei, Shaw-Wei Su, Hung-Yu Lai, Horng-Yuh Guo, Ting-Chien Chen, and Zueng-Sang Chen. 2010**"Remediation techniques and heavy metal uptake by different rice varieties in metal-contaminated soils of Taiwan: New aspects for food safety regulation and sustainable agriculture." *Soil Science & Plant Nutrition* 56, no. 1 : 31-52.
5. **Wuana, Raymond A., and Felix E. Okieimen. 2011.**"Heavy metals in contaminated soils: a review of sources, chemistry, risks and best available strategies for remediation." *International Scholarly Research Notices* 2011
6. **Alloway, Brian 2011.J., ed.** Heavy metals in soils: trace metals and metalloids in soils and their bioavailability. Vol. 22. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
7. **Nriagu, Jerome O. 1996.**"A history of global metal pollution." *Science* 272, no. 5259 223-223.
8. **Bilal, Muhammad, Ihsanullah Ihsanullah, Mohammad Younas, and Mansoor Ul Hassan Shah. 2021** "Recent advances in applications of low-cost adsorbents for the removal of heavy metals from water: A critical review." *Separation and Purification Technology* 278: 119510.
9. **Gusain, Rashi, Neeraj Kumar, and Suprakash Sinha Ray.2020** "Recent advances in carbon nanomaterial-based adsorbents for water purification." *Coordination Chemistry Reviews* 405 213111.
10. **Dlamini, Derrick S., John Michael Tesha, Gcina D. Vilakati, Bhekhe B. Mamba, Ajay K. Mishra, Justice M. Thwala, and Jianxin Li. 2020.**"A critical review of selected membrane-and powder-based adsorbents for water treatment: Sustainability and effectiveness." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 277: 123497.
11. **Saleh, Tawfik 2021 A.** "Protocols for synthesis of nanomaterials, polymers, and green materials as adsorbents for water treatment technologies." *Environmental Technology & Innovation* 24 101821.
12. **Crini, Grégorio.2005** "Recent developments in polysaccharide-based materials used as adsorbents in wastewater treatment." *Progress in polymer science* 30, no. 1 :38-70.
13. **Sachan, Deepa, Aiyagari Ramesh, and Gopal Das. 2021** "Green synthesis of silica nanoparticles from leaf biomass and its application to remove heavy metals from synthetic wastewater: A comparative analysis." *Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring & Management* 16 :100467.
14. **Sharma, Pratibha, Jaibir Kherb, Jai Prakash, and Raj Kaushal.2021** "A novel and facile green synthesis of SiO₂ nanoparticles for removal of toxic water pollutants." *Applied Nanoscience* 13, no. : 735-747.
15. **Wang, Yu-Ying, Yu-Xue Liu, Hao-Hao Lu, Rui-Qin Yang, and Sheng-Mao Yang. (2018):** "Competitive adsorption of Pb (II), Cu (II), and Zn (II) ions onto hydroxyapatite-biochar nanocomposite in aqueous solutions." *Journal of Solid State Chemistry* 261 53-61.
16. **Snehal, Sikha, and Pushpa Lohani. (2018):** "Silica nanoparticles: Its green synthesis and importance in agriculture." *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* 7, no. 5 3383-3393.
17. **Ali, Marwa, and AA-Ali Drea. (2021):** "Green synthesis and characterization of antibiotic amorphous nano silicon oxide powder extracted from rice husk ash." *International Journal of Current Research and Review* 13, no. 24 .94-99.
18. **Alhadhrami, A., Gehad G. Mohamed, Ahmed H. Sadek, Sameh H. Ismail, A. A. Ebnalwaled, and Abdurraheem SA Almalki. (2022)** "Behavior of silica nanoparticles synthesized from rice husk ash by the sol-gel method as a photocatalytic and antibacterial agent." *Materials* 15, no. 22: 8211.
19. **Nayak, P. P., and A. K. Datta. (2021)** "Synthesis of SiO₂-nanoparticles from rice husk ash and its comparison with commercial amorphous silica through material characterization." *Silicon* 13, no. 4): 1209-1214.
20. **Zhang, Zhiliang, Wenxiu He, Jianzhong Zheng, Guangquan Wang, and Jianbing Ji.2016.** "Rice husk ash-derived silica nanofluids: synthesis and stability study." *Nanoscale research letters* 11 : 1-8.
21. **Yadav, Virendra Kumar, and M. H. Fulekar.2019** "Green synthesis and characterization of amorphous silica nanoparticles from fly ash." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 18 (2019): 4351-4359.
22. **Sachan, Deepa, Aiyagari Ramesh, and Gopal Das. 2021** "Green synthesis of silica nanoparticles from leaf biomass and its application to remove heavy metals from synthetic wastewater: A comparative analysis." *Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring & Management* 16 (2021): 100467.
23. **Rajendran, Saravanan, A. K. Priya, P. Senthil Kumar, Tuan KA Hoang, Karthikeyan Sekar, Kar Yeen Chong, Kuan Shiong Khoo, Hui Suan Ng, and Pau Loke Show. 2022** "A critical and recent developments on adsorption technique for removal of heavy metals from wastewater-A review." *Chemosphere* 303 : 135146.
24. **Naseem, K., Q. Imran, M. Z. Ur Rehman, M. H. Tahir, and J. Najeeb. 2023** "Adsorptive removal of heavy metals and dyes from wastewater using *Azadirachta indica* biomass." *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 20, no. 5 (): 5799-5822.
25. **Usgodaarachchi, Leshan, Charitha Thambiliyagodage, Ramanee Wijesekera, and Martin G. Bakker. 2021** "Synthesis of mesoporous silica nanoparticles derived from rice husk and surface-controlled amine functionalization for efficient adsorption of methylene blue from aqueous solution." *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* 4 (): 100.116.
26. **Nguyen, Tan Tai.2021** "Effective Removal of Phosphate from Waste Water Based on Silica Nanoparticles." *Journal of Chemistry*
27. **De la Calle, Inmaculada, Mathieu Menta, Marlène Klein, and Fabienne Séby. 2017** "Screening of TiO₂ and Au nanoparticles in cosmetics and determination of elemental impurities by multiple techniques (DLS, SP-ICP-MS, ICP-MS and ICP-OES)." *Talanta* 171 (2017): 291-306.
28. **Punia, Pinki, Manish Kumar Bharti, Rakesh Dhar, Preeti Thakur, and Atul Thakur.2022** "Recent advances in detection and removal of heavy metals from contaminated water." *ChemBioEng Reviews* 9, no. 4: 351-369.
29. **Shahid, Muhammad, Camille Dumat, Sana Khalid, Nabeel Khan Niazi, and Paula MC Antunes. 2017** "Cadmium bioavailability, uptake, toxicity and detoxification in soil-plant system." *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* Volume 241 :73-137.
30. **Åkesson, Mrs Tanja, Codex Contact Point, and Viale delle Terme di Caracalla. 2015** "Joint FAO/WHO food

- standards programme codex committee on contaminants in foods." WHO, Geneva
31. **Järup, Lars. (2003)** "Hazards of heavy metal contamination." British medical bulletin 68, no. 1: 167-182.
 32. **Joint, F. A. O., 2011.** WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives, and World Health Organization. Safety evaluation of certain contaminants in food: prepared by the Seventy-second meeting of the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA). World Health Organization,.
 33. **Sachan, Deepa, Aiyagari Ramesh, and Gopal Das. 2021** "Green synthesis of silica nanoparticles from leaf biomass and its application to remove heavy metals from synthetic wastewater: A comparative analysis." Environmental Nanotechnology, Monitoring & Management 16 : 100467.
 34. **Wang, Weixing, Jarett C. Martin, Xiaotian Fan, Aijie Han, Zhiping Luo, and Luyi Sun.2012** "Silica nanoparticles and frameworks from rice husk biomass." ACS applied materials & interfaces 4, no. 2 : 977-981.
 35. **Chen, Haoran. 2013** "Biogenic silica nanoparticles derived from rice husk biomass and their applications."
 36. **Yuliasari, D. P., and S. D. Yuwono.2017** "Removal of Ni (II), Cu (II), and Zn (II) ions from aqueous solution using Tetraselmis sp. biomass modified with silica-coated magnetite nanoparticles." Desalination and Water Treatment 80: 203-213.
 37. **Mehta, S. K., and J. P. Gaur. 2005** "Use of algae for removing heavy metal ions from wastewater: progress and prospects." Critical reviews in biotechnology 25, no. 3: 113-152.